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CONSUMER BEHAVIOR MODELS: SUSTAINABLE EUROPEAN PRACTICES

Sustainable consumer behavior is a concept aimed at reducing the negative impact on the environment and society in the process of consuming goods and services. Consumer behavior patterns are becoming an increasingly important topic in the face of global environmental challenges and growing interest in sustainable development. The model includes a set of principles and actions aimed at minimizing negative impacts on the environment and society, as well as promoting ethical and responsible consumption practices.

The theory of models of sustainable consumer behavior correlates with the theory of sustainable development, therefore it includes three main components. Ecological consciousness. Involves consumers' awareness of the environmental consequences of their actions. Research shows that consumers with high levels of environmental consciousness are more likely to choose environmentally friendly products and services [1]. Consumers strive to minimize their environmental footprint by choosing products with low carbon emissions, minimal packaging and recyclability [2, 3]. Social responsibility. Consumers who are socially aware of their actions tend to choose products that contribute to better working conditions and social justice. Typically, brands and companies that demonstrate a commitment to social justice and inclusion are supported. Economic efficiency. It is assumed that the choice of goods and services is made considering their affordability and durability. Consumers strive for rational use of resources and avoid excess consumption. Sustainable consumers strive for optimal use of resources, minimizing waste and choosing products that last a long time and are of high quality. Variants of the model of sustainable consumer behavior differ according to the following criteria: product characteristics; environmental impact; impact on human health; cultural aspects and economic accessibility.

Model of consumption of environmentally friendly products that have minimal negative impact on the environment. With the emergence of the eco-friendly movement in the EU, this model has become widespread. It involves choosing certified products from producers who are responsible for the environment and biodiversity (these are products produced with a low carbon footprint; organic products) [4].

A pattern of food consumption that respects social norms and has a positive impact on society. Focuses on products that are produced without the use of forced child labor and comply with international conventions; products produced according to ethical standards. This includes products with a positive impact on the local economy [3]. Locally produced products; products produced in enterprises that create more jobs, as well as promote the economic and social inclusion of workers or respect for animal rights and regulations. Model of consumption of “healthy” foods with a certain nutrient composition. The object of consumer choice is food products that meet healthy nutrition standards, without toxic and dangerous ingredients; creating conditions for a favorable food environment. In general, the higher a consumer's awareness of environmental issues and their impacts, the more likely they are to make sustainable purchasing decisions. Personal values and beliefs have a significant influence on consumer behavior, including environmental and social responsibility priorities. Availability and transparency of information about a product and its eco-efficiency play an important role in shaping consumer preferences.

Conclusions. Sustainable consumer behavior is an important component of sustainable development. It requires awareness of the environmental, social and economic aspects of consumption, as well as a willingness to make informed and responsible decisions. The use of theories and models of consumer behavior helps to better understand the mechanisms of consumer choice formation, which allows us to develop effective strategies for promoting goods/services. Promoting sustainable consumer behavior requires both educational initiatives to raise public awareness and policy measures to encourage the development of sustainable production and consumption practices. It is important to note that the transition to sustainable consumption requires the joint efforts of all market participants: consumers, producers and government institutions.

References

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